

Utilizing OSM data in geospatial representation learning

Piotr Gramacki^{1,*}, Kacper Leśniara¹, Kamil Raczycki¹, Szymon Woźniak¹ and Piotr Szymański¹

¹ Department of Artificial Intelligence / Kraina.AI Lab, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Wrocław, Poland; piotr.gramacki@pwr.edu.pl, klesniara@kraina.ai, kraczycki@kraina.ai, swozniak@kraina.ai, piotr.szymanski@pwr.edu.pl

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

This abstract was accepted to the OSM Science 2023 Conference after peer-review.

Representation learning has been proven to be a very capable approach in many domains of artificial intelligence like Natural Language Processing (NLP) [1,2], Computer Vision (CV) [3,4] or Network Science (NS) [5]. Representation learning of spatial and geographic data is a rapidly developing field that allows for similarity detection between areas and high-quality inference using deep neural networks. Existing approaches concentrate on embedding raster imagery (maps, street or satellite photos), mobility data or road networks. We propose methods for learning vector representations of OpenStreetMap regions concerning urban functions, land use, POI location and road network with additional features. We also propose an approach to include public transport availability in the representation learning approach. We have designed our representation learning methods operating on various types of OpenStreetMap (OSM) data, one of the largest open databases with structured geospatial data. All our methods make use of a hierarchical spatial index to increase reproducibility. We utilize Uber's H3 geospatial indexing system [6] that partitions the space into uniquely identifiable hexagonal regions. We presented our results at different workshops accompanying the SIGSPATIAL conference.

Our methods are available in an open-source Python library - *Spatial Representations for Artificial Intelligence (srai)* [7] designed for working with geospatial data. The library can download geospatial data, split a given area into microregions using multiple algorithms and train an embedding model using various architectures. It includes baseline models as well as more complex methods from published works. Those capabilities make it possible to use *srai* in a complete pipeline for geospatial task solving. An exemplary outcome of one of the available methods is depicted in Figure 1. We hope our library will take the first steps to standardize the geospatial AI domain. The library is fully open-source and published under the Apache 2.0 license.

In our first research paper [8], we utilize a key/tag metadata structure bound to every object in the OSM to create contextual embeddings and use it to predict bicycle-sharing systems' (BSS) stations' location. Laying out a bike-sharing system is critical in addressing the increase in bike demand. We address the problem of cost and time in BSS layout design and propose a new solution to streamline and facilitate the process of such planning by

Gramacki, P., Leśniara, K., Raczycki, K., Woźniak, S., & Szymański, P. (2023). Utilising OSM data in geospatial representation learning In: Minghini, M., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., Liu, P., Yeboah, G., Juhász, L., Coetzee, S., Mooney, P., Sarretta, A., & Anderson, J. (Eds.). Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023, Antwerp, Belgium, 10-12 November 2023. Available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/osmscience-2023>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10443338](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443338)

© 2023 by the authors. Available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution ([CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)) license.

using spatial embedding methods. Based only on publicly available data from OpenStreetMap and station layouts from 34 cities in Europe, a method has been developed to divide cities into microregions using the Uber H3 discrete global grid system and to indicate regions where it is worth placing a station based on existing systems in different cities using transfer learning. The result of the work is a mechanism to support planners in their decision-making when planning a station layout with a choice of reference cities.

Figure 1. Embeddings of regions represented in RGB colour space in Wrocław, Poland.

Secondly, in hex2vec [9], we worked with the same data type and proposed a word2vec-style [1] embedding method that yields semantic aware embeddings via the Skip-gram model [10] with negative sampling [11]. The resulting vector representations showcase semantic structures of the map characteristics, similar to ones found in vector-based language models. Through manual verification of tagging quality, we selected 36 cities for training region representations. We also present insights from region similarity detection in six Polish cities and propose a region typology obtained through agglomerative clustering.

We also propose a highway2vec method [12] to embed network structures with an autoencoder neural network. This method generates microregions' embeddings concerning their road infrastructure characteristics. We obtained vector representations that detect how similar map hexagons are in the road networks they contain. Additionally, we observe that embeddings yield a latent space with meaningful arithmetic operations. Finally, clustering methods allowed us to draft a high-level typology of obtained representations.

Finally, in gtfs2vec [13], we reach external data sources to represent public transport availability in our embedding methods. We use public transport schedules publicly available in the GTFS format. We selected 48 European cities and gathered their public transport timetables. We utilized Uber's H3 spatial index to divide each city into hexagonal micro-regions. Based on the timetables data, we created certain features describing the quantity and variety of public transport availability in each region. Next, we trained an auto-associative deep neural network to embed each region. Later, we used a hierarchical clustering approach to identify similar regions. Finally, we analyzed the obtained clusters at

different levels to identify some number of clusters that qualitatively describe public transport availability. We showed that our typology matches the characteristics of analyzed cities and allows successful searching for areas with similar public transport schedule characteristics.

We argue that the geospatial artificial intelligence domain needs its *huggingface moment*. Huggingface [14,15] standardized research in Natural Language Processing, providing unified interfaces for models, benchmark datasets and more. Such easy access to models and evaluation data encourages researchers to present their results reproducibly. The geospatial domain needs just this since it is often challenging to reproduce results. It can result from closed-source data or hard-to-reproduce training code. With our library and our models' inclusion, we want to contribute towards standardizing the geospatial artificial intelligence domain.

While Huggingface has set a standardization precedent in the NLP domain, we do not position ourselves as its direct equivalent in geospatial AI. Our primary objective is to highlight the need for a unified approach in this domain. Our contributions aim to initiate a dialogue on GeoAI standardization, emphasizing reproducibility and accessibility.

References

- [1] Mikolov, T., Sutskever, I., Chen, K., Corrado, G. S., & Dean, J. (2013). Distributed Representations of Words and Phrases and their Compositionality. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 26.
- [2] Peters M. E., Neumann M., Iyyer M., Gardner M., Clark C., Lee K., & Zettlemoyer L. (2018). Deep Contextualized Word Representations. In M. Walker, H. Ji, & A. Stent (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2018 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long Papers)*, 2227–2237. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [3] Feichtenhofer C., Fan H., Xiong B., Girshick R., & He K. (2021). A Large-Scale Study on Unsupervised Spatiotemporal Representation Learning. *2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 3298–3308.
- [4] Ghosh R., Jia X., Yin L., Lin C., Jin Z., & Kumar V. (2022). Clustering Augmented Self-Supervised Learning: An Application to Land Cover Mapping. In Renz, M., Sarwat, M., Nascimento, M. A., Shekhar, S., & Xie, X. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Advances in Geographic Information Systems (ACM SIGSPATIAL '22)*, 3. The Association for Computing Machinery.
- [5] Zhang, D., Yin, J., Zhu, X., & Zhang, C. (2017). Network Representation Learning: A Survey. *IEEE Transactions on Big Data*, 6(1), 3-28.
- [6] Uber Technologies Inc. (2018). *H3: Uber's hexagonal hierarchical spatial index | Uber Blog*. <https://www.uber.com/blog/h3>
- [7] Gramacki, P., Leśniara, K., Raczycki, K., Woźniak, S., Przymus, M., & Szymański, P. (2023). SRAI: Towards Standardization of Geospatial AI. In S. Newsam, L. Yang, G. Mai, B. Martins, D. Lunga & S. Gao (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 6th ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on AI for Geographic Knowledge Discovery (GeoAI '23)*. 43–52. The Association for Computing Machinery.
- [8] Raczycki, K. & Szymański, P. (2021). Transfer learning approach to bicycle-sharing systems' station location planning using OpenStreetMap data. In B. Kar, S. Mohebbi, G. Fu, X. Ye, & O. A. Omitaomu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 4th ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on Advances in Resilient and Intelligent Cities (ARIC '21)*, 1–12. The Association for Computing Machinery.
- [9] Woźniak, S. & Szymański, P. (2021). Hex2vec: Context-Aware Embedding H3 Hexagons with OpenStreetMap Tags. In D. Lunga, L. Yang, S. Gao, B. Martins, Y. Hu, X. Deng, & S. Nesam (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 4th ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on AI for Geographic Knowledge Discovery (GEOAI '21)*, 61–71. The Association for Computing Machinery.

- [10] Mikolov, T., Chen, K., Corrado, G.S., & Dean, J. (2013). *Efficient Estimation of Word Representations in Vector Space*. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1301.3781>
- [11] Bojanowski P., Grave E., Joulin A., & Mikolov T. (2017). Enriching Word Vectors with Subword Information. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 5, 135–146.
- [12] Leśniara, K. & Szymański, P. (2021). Highway2vec: representing OpenStreetMap microregions with respect to their road network characteristics. In B. Martins, D., Lunga, S. Gao, S. Newsam, L. Yang, X. Deng, & G. Mai (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 5th ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on AI for Geographic Knowledge Discovery (GEOAI '22)*, 18-29. The Association for Computing Machinery.
- [13] Gramacki, P., Woźniak, S. & Szymański, P. (2021). Gtfs2vec: Learning GTFS Embeddings for comparing Public Transport Offer in Microregions. In G. Cavallaro, B. Heras, D. Lunga, M. Werner, & A. Züfle (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 1st ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on Searching and Mining Large Collections of Geospatial Data (GeoSearch'21)*, 5-12. The Association for Computing Machinery.
- [14] Lhoest, Q., Villanova del Moral, A., von Platen, P., Wolf, T., Šaško, M., Jernite, Y., Thakur, A., Tunstall, L., Patil, S., Drame, M., Chaumond, J., Plu, J., Davison, J., Brandeis, S., Sanh, V., Le Scao, T., Canwen Xu, K., Patry, N., Liu, S., McMillan-Major, A., Schmid, P., Gugger, S., Raw, N., Lesage, S., Lozhkov, A., Carrigan, M., Matussière, T., von Werra, L., Debut, L., Bekman, S., & Delangue, C. (2021). Datasets: A Community Library for Natural Language Processing. In H. Adel, & S. Shi (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations*, 175–184. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [15] Wolf, T., Debut, L., Sanh, V., Chaumond, J., Delangue, C., Moi, A., Cistac, P., Ma, C., Jernite, Y., Plu, J., Xu, C., Le Scao, T., Gugger, S., Drame, M., Lhoest, Q., & Rush, A. M. (2020). Transformers: State-of-the-Art Natural Language Processing. In Q. Liu, & D. Schlangen (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations*, 38–45. Association for Computational Linguistics.